

UDK: 629.113

FORMATION AND REPAIR OF ROADS FORMATION OF ELECTRONIC BASE.

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Annotation. This article discusses the wide range of possibilities of the electronic database of construction and repair of roads, the economic efficiency of the electronic database in the construction and repair of highways, simplification of construction and repair work, better quality of construction processes.

Keywords: Construction, repair of roads, Roads, Electronic database.

Introduction. The development of information technology and the increasing flow of information, the rapid change of data are urging humanity to look for new ways to process data in a timely manner. As we know, the rapid development of information systems and the rapid growth of data led to the creation of a special software package called "Database Management System" (DBMS) in the early 60's.

When creating a database, the user tries to sort the information by different characters and quickly select them with any combination of characters. This can only be done in a structured way, using database management systems (DBMS).

A database is an organized collection of interconnected data on a disk. In other words, a database is a specific structured, interconnected, and sequential set of data written into computer memory that does not store the properties, status, or relationships between objects. lum in the sense [1].

In accordance with the Presidential Decree "On measures to implement the program of development of regional highways in 2017-2018", the existing inter-farm rural highways, cities, urban settlements, rural and aul streets step-by-step registration and their certification, the creation of an electronic database on the results of work in this area [2].

Materials and methods. The article used the methods of comparative analysis, study and nationalization of foreign experience, study and field orientation of technologies, logic and generalization.

The main part. As a result of the reforms being carried out in the new Uzbekistan, openness, the development of international economic and political relations will create opportunities for the modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of industrial sectors in our country. An example of this is the growth of our country's foreign trade. Many terms, such as "e-government", "e-government", "telecommunications", "Internet", "website" have become an integral part of our lives. IT covers all areas of our daily lives.

An important aspect of shaping and implementing the digital economy is, first of all, the implementation of the state's regional policy aimed at solving the following problems. It is necessary to increase investment attractiveness and increase innovation activity in the regions, develop production and social infrastructure, minimize regional disparities in the field of socio-economic development of regions, strengthen interregional relations and rational use of human potential [5].

Errors in the selection of the data model can have a decisive impact on the implementation of the necessary functions in the GAT and the further expansion of their list, as well as on the cost-effectiveness of the project. The choice of data model is directly related to the value of the geographical and attribute databases that are formed.

The most common model of data organization is the layered model (Figure 1). The essence of the model is that the objects are divided into thematic layers and a series of objects belonging to a single layer. It turns out that the objects of a separate layer are stored in a separate file, which has its own system of identifiers, which can be referred to as a collection. As can be seen in Figure 1, industrial areas, shopping malls, bus routes, roads, and census areas are categorized. Often a single thematic layer is divided horizontally, as are separate sheets of maps. This is done for ease of MB administration and to avoid working with large data files.

figure 1. An example of layered data organization.

Within a layered model, there are two specific realizations: vector-topological and vector-notopological models.

In recent years, GPS tracking has become more common in everyday life, and is referred to as the Global Positioning System. The system consists of a network of satellites that continuously send electromagnetic signals to Earth.

The result. Road construction and maintenance is a complex process. Because it takes a lot of effort and money. If all the money spent on road construction is directed to the desired goals, the extra costs will be avoided. This is the main idea and purpose of our electronic database. The electronic database

of construction and repair of highways affects the quality and service life of roads. In other words, the funds allocated by the republic for highways will be directed to a specific area and location, based on information received through an electronic database for construction and repair work. Allocated funds will be prevented from looting. Expenditures will be monitored and roads will be improved. We have created a model for our region of the first electronic database for the construction and repair of roads. In the future, the coverage of this database will be expanded. An electronic database for the construction and repair of roads in all regions will be formed. All electronic databases will be updated and enriched. This allows you to share information in a new way.

figure 2. General information about the single electronic database of highways in Namangan region:

figure 3. A window that belongs to the same district roads:

Through this window we can get the latest information about the existing roads in only one district, the roads to be built, the roads under repair, the existing artificial structures on the highways. . We can obtain information electronically from the road construction organization responsible for these roads, its staff, and available road construction equipment. It also provides information on local and domestic routes.

figure 4. A window with information about the existing artificial structures and cladding in the region:

Conclusion. In the decrees of February 14, 2017 "On measures to further improve the system of road management" stage registration and their certification, creation of an electronic database on the results of work in this area [3]. This will increase the scope and quality of work through the process. Because the evaluation and control of work done through the electronic database will increase.

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